

IN-SITU STRAIN MEASUREMENT IN ADAPTIVE COMPOSITES USING FIBER BRAGG GRATING SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

Adaptive composites have been produced by embedding thin pre-strained shape memory alloy (SMA) wires into a Kevlar-epoxy host material. The resulting material demonstrates attractive effects such as a shape change, a controlled overall thermal expansion or a shift in the natural vibration frequency upon activation. The working principle is that pre-strained martensitic shape memory alloys tend to recover their initial shape when heated above their transformation temperature. If the wires are clamped externally or because they are embedded into a host material, the wire strain recovery is limited, and large recovery stresses are instead generated, which may lead to the effects cited above. In addition, if one desires to manufacture a material that combines activation and sensing capabilities, a sensor must also be incorporated into the host composite, to directly measure the activation effect and control it. To this end, Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors have been embedded into adaptive composites, and the strain measured in-situ during activation. The effect of temperature on the response of the Bragg sensor has been taken into account in order to measure the exact fiber strain. In the case of Kevlar-epoxy host materials, the strain is always negative as the effects of negative thermal coefficient of the host and SMA contraction add up. The effect of manufacturing conditions, and hence initial stress state in the composite before activation on the magnitude of strain are discussed. Finally, results of the stress and strain simulation are compared with the experimental data, and guidelines are provided for optimization of this smart material.

Keywords: Adaptive composites, Smart materials, Shape memory alloys, Fiber Bragg grating sensors, strain measurement.

INTRODUCTION

The natural evolution of structural materials for the past 40 years is moving from the search for high specific properties, through the need to reduce manufacturing and production costs towards a greater flexibility and functionality of the part. Since conventional structural composite materials cannot fulfill this last requirement, adaptive or smart composite materials provide a potential path for further structural developments. Adaptive materials can change some of their properties in response to environmental fluctuations by the integration of actuating and sensing technologies. A possible approach to these materials is the integration of thin Shape Memory Alloy (SMA) wires as actuating elements in fiber reinforced polymer composites [1-3]. Shape Memory Alloys have been available for 40 years and have found some applications as actuators, but have been only recently manufactured as high quality wires with diameters below 0.2 mm. This allows the direct integration of SMA wires into fiber reinforced polymer composites without losing the structural integrity of the matrix material. In comparison to other actuating technologies, SMAs offer additional important advantages: high

reversible strains (up to 6%), high damping capacity, large reversible changes of mechanical and physical characteristics, and most importantly, the ability to generate extremely high recovery stresses (up to 800 MPa) [4]. Their main drawback is the need to heat up the structure to activate it, and the relatively slow response, since heat transfer controls the kinetics.

As a result, composite materials with SMA wires demonstrate attractive effects such as a shape change, a controlled overall thermal expansion or a shift in the natural vibration frequency upon activation. The working principle is that pre-strained martensitic shape memory alloys tend to recover their initial shape when heated above their transformation temperature. If the wires are clamped externally or they are embedded into a host material, the wire strain recovery is limited, and large recovery stresses are instead generated, which may lead to the effects cited above.

In addition to the activation induced by the SMA wires, if one desires to manufacture a material that combines activation and sensing capabilities, a sensor must also be incorporated into the host composite. To this end, Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors have been embedded into adaptive composites, and the strain measured in-situ during activation. The operating principle of a FBG sensor can be summarized in the property of the grating to reflect from a broadband source only the so-called Bragg wavelength λ_B that matches the grating pitch Λ , through the equation:

$$\lambda_B = 2n \quad (1)$$

where n is the mean index of refraction of the fibre core [5]. A Bragg wavelength change is induced when the sensor is thermally or mechanically strained, due to its physical elongation (with a corresponding change in the grating pitch) and to the strain- and/or temperature-related change in the fibre index. Thus, if the temperature and strain behaviour of the sensor is adequately characterised, internal strain information can be recovered in the composite during activation tests by monitoring temperature and Bragg wavelength changes.

This article reports recent results on the manufacturing of adaptive composites containing SMA wires and a FBG sensor. Internal strain during manufacturing and during activation are measured, and compared with theoretical results based on the wire thermomechanical behavior and a simple force balance with the host material. Guidelines are hence provided to manufacture composite with the desired response.

MATERIALS

The host material consists of unidirectional aligned Kevlar® 29 aramid fibres and LTM217 epoxy resin, manufactured in the form of prepregs by Advanced Composites Group (UK). The fibre volume fraction is about 60%. The material is chosen because of the rather low curing temperature of the epoxy and the insulating properties of both components. The Kevlar fibres, which are 12 μm in diameter, have a negative thermal expansion coefficient of $-5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and a Young's modulus that is similar to that of the SMA wires (about 70 GPa).

The wires are 150 μm diameter NiTiCu wires manufactured by Furukawa (Japan), which are martensitic at room temperature, and have the following transformation temperatures: the martensitic transformation range is between -20 and 35°C , and the austenitic range is between 52 and 77°C . Properties of this wire are given in Ref. [2].

The FBG sensors used in this study are written in acrylate- or polyimide-coated, standard monomode optical fibres. Two of the three fibres used are made with polyacrylate coatings, which has a theoretical maximum application temperature of 177°C , the third is made of polyimide with a service temperature ($< T_g$) greater than 240°C . The gratings are fabricated at IOA, EPFL, and are centred at $\lambda_B=1540\text{nm}$, with a 0.8 or 3mm gauge length. The fibres are stripped of the coating and treated with silane in the region of the grating, to ensure good adhesion with the surrounding epoxy matrix, hence an optimized stress transfer between the sensor and the matrix.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Sample manufacturing:

The specimens are prepared in a specifically designed frame that allows the pre-straining and alignment of the SMA wires [1,3,6,7]. A single FBG sensor is embedded in the prepreg stack in a 0.5 mm gap between two SMA wires. Prior to embedding, the surface of the optical fibre is cleaned with ethanol and dried. To optimise the interfacial adhesion a surface treatment of 2% Silane (Sylquest A-1100) with 2% distilled water in isopropanol solution is applied for one hour. Drying takes place for two hours at 80°C. The optical fibre is also aligned and pre-strained with a second device using a micrometer-screw to avoid any compressive load, buckling and misalignment of the fibre during processing and in service. The wires and the optical fiber are thus both in the same plane, at the mid-thickness of the sample. The SMA wires are pre-strained at 3% and the optical fibre at about 0.1%. The composite is fabricated by laying up the chosen number of prepreg layers symmetrically above and below the SMA wires and optical fibre. The assembly is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: SMA composite with one frame to prestrain the SMA wires by 3% and one device to maintain one optical fibre with an integrated Bragg grating strained at 0.1%.

The detection system used to determine the Bragg peak wavelength is a tunable laser combined with a photodetector. The Labview-controlled Photonetics laser diode source scans the wavelength range of interest with a resolution of 5 pm and the reflected light is collected by a photodetector. The data is acquired on PC by means of a National Instruments card and Labview software. To monitor the strain evolution during the curing process in an autoclave, the optical fibre is fed through the vacuum bag sealing tape and the pressure port of the autoclave to the detection system.

Three samples were prepared using the described technique, and their characteristics are given in Table 1. The cure cycle was 12h at 70 °C in an autoclave under vacuum-pressure only, followed by a post-cure for 4 hours at 140°C, either in the frame, or outside the frame.

Specimen	Dimensions [mm]	V_f SMA	FBG type	FBG length [mm]	p_e	S_T	Post-cure
1	150 x 12.2 x 0.43	5.4	acrylate	3	0.2142	7.17×10^{-6}	No
2	150 x 12.8 x 0.40	5.5	acrylate	3	0.2270	8.47×10^{-6}	Free
3	150 x 12.6 x 0.55	4.0	polyimide	0.8	0.2780	7.60×10^{-6}	In frame

Table 1: Composite specimen characteristics

All samples were well impregnated, with a good distribution of the Kevlar fibres around the SMA wires [6,7]. 16 SMA actuators were embedded in each sample. The sensors were marked and placed in the middle of the composite samples, (position 75 / 6.5 ±0.3 mm) in their neutral axis. A serial electrical connection was then made between the SMA wires outside the sample to allow for Joule heating of the wires during the activation tests.

Temperature and Strain calibration of the FBG sensors:

A Bragg wavelength change $\Delta\lambda_B$ is induced when the sensor is thermally or mechanically strained, due to its physical elongation (with a corresponding change in the grating pitch) and to the strain- and/or temperature-related change in the fibre index. Two effects contribute to a wavelength shift due to a temperature variation: the thermal expansion of the fibre, and a change in the index of refraction of the fibre core. The latter is in most cases the dominating mechanism. In the general case, the response of a Bragg grating written in a monomode fibre to thermal as well as axial mechanical loading can be expressed as [5]:

$$\frac{\lambda_B}{\lambda_B} = (1 - p_e) \epsilon_z + S_T T \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_z is the axial strain in the fibre, $\Delta\lambda_B$ is the Bragg wavelength shift, and ΔT is the temperature variation, S_T is the temperature sensitivity coefficient and p_e is the effective photoelastic coefficient. The sensors must therefore be calibrated with respect to both strain and temperature, i.e. both the p_e and the S_T constants need to be determined experimentally. The first of the two constants is determined by performing a simple uniaxial tensile test at room temperature, using small weights suspended to the fibre. The Bragg wavelength shift $\Delta\lambda_B$ is monitored as the fibre is strained longitudinally, and the $(1-p_e)$ value can be obtained as the slope of the graph of $\Delta\lambda_B/\lambda_B$ versus the applied strain ϵ_z . Due to its configuration, the test is load-controlled and the longitudinal strain is derived from the longitudinal stress in the fibre, using the fibre Young's modulus $E_f = 72$ GPa. This is to avoid the mechanical contribution of the fibre coating, which is less stiff than the fibre, influencing the measurement. As for the temperature calibration, the unstrained sensor is placed in an oven and simultaneous temperature and wavelength readings are taken at regular intervals in a heating cycle from 25° to 110 °C. Experimental results are shown in Figure 2 for Sample 1.

Figure 2: Temperature calibration of Bragg grating sensor (Sample 1)

It is generally known that the thermal expansion of the fibre is usually negligible with respect to the change in the index of refraction of the fibre core in temperature-related Bragg wavelength shifts. This is also the case for the fibres used in this work: the experimentally measured shift (dotted line in Fig.2) in a temperature calibration test is considerably greater than that obtained by considering only a thermal expansion of the fibre (solid line). The latter is calculated using a thermal expansion coefficient of $5.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ for glass. Thus, the variation of the fibre index with temperature is

henceforth considered the mechanism responsible for wavelength shifts due to temperature. This assumption allows the “rescaling” of the measured wavelength shifts in tests, by purging the contribution due to temperature variations, so as to obtain correct strain measurements in the composite specimens. The experimentally derived values for the p_e and S_T constants are given in Table 1 for the three sensors used in specimens 1, 2 and 3.

STRAIN MEASUREMENT DURING CURE

One fibre Bragg grating sensor was used to monitor the strain evolution during the curing cycle of the composite. Figure 3 shows a plot of the strain induced in the optical sensor during the curing process of sample 3 in the autoclave. The second axis represents the program temperature.

Figure 3: Evolution of induced strain during composite production of Sample 3

From the lay-up process prior to the heating cycle, the optical fibre was prestrained by 0.1 %. To account only for the deformation during cure, all values are thus shifted down by 0.1%, so that strain starts at 0. During the heating cycle the aluminium frame holding the optical fibre under pre-strain expanded and a tensile strain was induced in the optical fibre. After the gelation time of about 4 hours and 40 minutes, the curing shrinkage began to affect the system. During the cooling step the strain was released and became compressive. For the post-curing cycle the sample and its frame were placed in an oven preheated to 45°C, and the optical fibre was released from its straining frame. During the following 5 hours it was heated to 140°C. Here the effect of the contracting SMA wires is observed, together with that of the Kevlar fibres. The compressive strain is partially relaxed during the cooling ramp, though significant strain still remained in the sample. Upon releasing the sample from the frame, the compressive strain was largely maintained. The stresses corresponding to the minimum and residual strain levels in Figure 3 were -44MPa and -32MPa respectively. These results are consistent with results from Psarras, et. al. [8] who produced composites of the same materials made with two unidirectional Kevlar / epoxy plies embedding 5 and 20 NiTiCu wires of 0.15 mm in diameter. They analysed the composite during and after the curing cycle using Raman spectroscopy with the 514.5 nm line of an Ar-ion laser as excitation length. The laser was polarised along the Kevlar reinforcing fibres to measure the residual stress state after composite production. With this method they obtained total residual stress levels of -52.5 MPa and -13.5 MPa for composites with 2.6 % and 10.6 % wire volume fraction respectively. A composite with the wire volume fraction of 4 % should thereby exhibit stresses in between these two values, which is in reasonable agreement to the above case.

STRAIN MEASUREMENT DURING ACTIVATION

Strain measurements with the optical fibre sensors were carried out in a U-shaped sample holder, described in details in Ref. [9] and presented in Figure 4. It consists in a frame in which the sample can be clamped on one or both ends, heated with a current source by Joule effect, and a full Wheatstone bridge records the strain (hence the force exerted by the sample) in the holder. Temperature is monitored during the test with a small thermocouple glued to the surface of the sample with conductive paste. The first run of each series involved clamping the sample at both ends in the holder. This configuration allowed comparison of the average strain measured with the Wheatstone bridge with that of the local Bragg sensor. Once the strain value of the FBG sensor has been verified, the sample was simply clamped and activated whilst recording time, temperature and the Bragg wavelength.

Figure 4 – Adaptive composite sample with an embedded FBG sensor, mounted on the testing device

A second wavelength detection system, commercially available from MicronOptics was used in these experiments. It differed from the one presented before in its acquisition speed, as it detected the position of the reflected “Bragg” peak without performing a complete scan over a frequency range, reaching measurement frequencies of up to 5 Hz.

Figure 5. Activation run of Sample 1 in clamped-clamped configuration

An initial run was carried out clamping the Sample No. 1 from both ends to compare the measurements taken with the Wheatstone bridge with those produced by the optical measuring system. Figure 5 thus exhibits the stress measured from the calibrated bridge, as F/S , where F is the measured force, and S is the composite section, and the strain measured in the optic fibre. Good

agreement between both measuring techniques is observed, the composite contracts as expected by the combined effects of the SMA wire activation and the negative CTE of Kevlar-epoxy. This experiment also allows confirmation of the value of the rigidity of the sample holder, measured independently as $k=570$ N/mm. Indeed, the apparent rigidity $\Delta F = k \Delta L$, where L is the distance of 105mm between clamps, corresponds to 11GPa, which is in agreement with the values of E_c measured on the graph. Once the measurement technique was validated, experiments with free-standing samples were carried out and ‘internal’ strain measurements were taken from the optical fibre gratings inside the laminates. The internal stress was then calculated as $E_c \epsilon$, where E_c is the modulus of the sample, about 40 GPa, assuming a perfect stress transfer between the optical fibre and the host composite.

Figure 6: Stress-strain vs. temperature plot during activation run of Sample 1 in clamped-clamped and simply clamped (free) configuration.

Figure 6 presents a comparison of the stress and strain measured from the optical fiber as a function of temperature, for both clamped and free configurations. Note that for the sake of clarity, stresses and strains are presented positive, but correspond to compressive strains and stresses. The results demonstrate the clamping effect on the recovery of the composites: in the clamped state, the composite exerts a stress on the holder to reach about 25 MPa at 100°C, resulting in a force balance between the sample holder, representing a structure, and the composite it is attached to. In the free state, the sample is free to compress to the maximum value of 0.12% at 100°C, leading to an internal stress value of about 50 MPa. As in refs.[1,2] a narrow hysteresis loop corresponding to the thermomechanical behaviour of the embedded NiTiCu actuators, could be observed. The straight line in Figure 6 presents the theoretical thermal behaviour of the host composite with no embedded wire in it. It is observed that the effect of the SMA wires on the composite strain is significant, and with the proper choice of NiTiCu wires and amount of pre-strain, preserves a linear behaviour, potentially suited for further control applications.

The three samples produced are compared in Figure 7 in terms of strain. The first sample, which was not postcured, exhibits a slightly higher slope. Sample 2 and 3 were post-cured, with sample 2 released from the frame, and sample 3 kept in the frame. Sample 3 had a lower volume fraction wires and its stress-temperature curve is indeed slightly below the other samples. Overall, variations in volume fraction and post-curing conditions do not seem to exert an influence on the final strain behaviour of the composites. A practical consequence is that as long as the samples do not buckle during post-cure, it is possible to post-cure them out of the frame. Finally, the values of internal stress found by this technique are once again in general agreement with those of Parthenios et al. [10].

Figure 7: Activation run of Samples 1, 2 and 3 in free configuration.

MODELLING OF STRESSES AND STRAIN WITH RC LOOP

The next step in designing with these adaptive materials is to provide tools, which predict the composite behaviour as a function of the host composite and the wire thermomechanical properties. To this end, a model called RC Loop, which was initially designed to describe the thermomechanical behaviour of single wires, was adapted to take into account the presence of the host matrix [11-14]. The composite strain is obtained by a simple force balance, such that

$$\sigma_{comp}(T) = \sigma_m - \alpha_c (T - T_{rs}) \quad (3)$$

where T_{rs} is the temperature at which the constrained thermal load starts, α_c the CTE of the host composite, E_c the Young's modulus of the host composite, and σ_m the stress in the host composite. The latter is related to the stress exerted by a wire σ_w , which is calculated at each step with RC Loop as follows:

$$\sigma_m = \frac{V_f}{1 - V_f} \sigma_w \quad (4)$$

Finally, the modulus of the entire composite is written with a rule of mixtures from the moduli of the host composite and wire:

$$E_{comp} = V_f E_w + (1 - V_f) E_c \quad (5)$$

The matrix modulus, E^c , is considered to be temperature independent in a first approximation, while the Young's modulus of the wire, E^w , is temperature dependent and hysteretic. The thermal dependence of the SMA composite beam Young's modulus $E^{comp} = E^{comp}(T)$ hence inherits the non-linearity and hysteresis from the Martensitic Transformation of the embedded SMA wire. Simulations of the SMA composite behaviour always start by the deformation of the SMA wire in the austenitic state and proceed up to the required prestrain level, ϵ^c . Then the general constraint is imposed and the simulation continues by thermal cycling between the prescribed upper and lower temperature or stress limits. The parameters necessary to model the behaviour of a single NiTiCu wire are presented in Refs.[10-13].

Figure 8: Simulated composite strain versus temperature for various wire volume fractions

Figure 8 presents the results of the RCLoop simulation of the strain versus temperature for various volume fractions of SMA wire pre-strained 3%, embedded in the host Kevlar-epoxy composite with $E_c=40\text{GPa}$ and $\alpha_c=-3 \cdot 10^{-6}$. The shape of the curves is in general agreement with the experimental results, and the effect of wire volume fraction is clearly observed: a higher V_f induces higher strain, and increases the width of the hysteresis loop. Note that the initial strain value is about -0.0004 , which means that there is a slight tensile strain in the composite, if we consider the 0 strain state at the fabrication temperature of $T_{rs}=140^\circ\text{C}$. This is indeed confirmed by the experimental strain measured Figure 3, where a strain increase between -0.12% and -0.08% is observed from the end of post-cure at 140°C , until room temperature. Comparison with Figure 3, however, reveals that the assumption of zero strain in the composite at the end of post-cure is clearly not accurate. Finally, the magnitude of strain during activation, shown in Figure 8, is underestimated by the model, since for $V_f=5\%$, the model predicts about 0.7% strain over 100°C , when 0.12% is observed in practice. This is due to a non-adequate prediction of the wire stress in the RCLoop program with the current choice of parameters. Indeed, if one considers the wire stress found experimentally in a single wire test, values of 600MPa are found [2], which lead to a strain value of 0.11% using Eq.4 and 5, in better agreement with the experimental results. Additional research to refine the model parameters is in progress.

CONCLUSION

Adaptive composite based on Kevlar-epoxy host matrices with embedded pre-strained NiTiCu shape memory alloy wires were produced. The hybrid composite additionally contained a Fibre Bragg Grating in an optical fibre, in order to monitor the strain in the composite, both during production and during activation. These materials were shown to exhibit significant negative strains when heated. Using the RC Loop program, it was shown that the strain resulting from activation is a function of the host material properties, the wire behaviour and wire volume fraction. Further refinements of the thermomechanical model are however needed to render the accurate stress level in the wire during activation. This work is a first step towards the manufacturing and design of composite parts exhibiting acting and sensing functionalities. Potential applications of these “smart” composites are the active dimensional stability control of structures, health monitoring coupled to active repair, and active shape control of composite parts.

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